

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF SI-N=C=N CONTAINING PRECERAMIC POLYMERS

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SUMMARY: In the paper, a kind of novel precursors with Si-N=C=N in the main chains were synthesized and characterized. The mediocre ceramic yields were obtained after heattreatment for $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ and crosslinking treatment for $[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$.

KEYWORDS: precursor, Si-N=C=N unit, pyrolysis, ceramic yield

INTRODUCTION

Since the successful applications of organosilicon precursors in manufacturing ceramic fibres (e.g., Nicalon fibre) [1] and ultrafine powders [2], and the potential advantages in manufacturing complex, continuous fibre reinforced ceramic composites [3], much effort has been focused on devising novel precursors with high ceramic yields and good processability. The precursors ever studied usually bear the main chains with Si-C, Si-C-C, Si-N, Si-Si-N, Si-N-N, etc., leading to Si-C, Si-N, Si-C-N ceramics upon pyrolysis [4-8]. Here we reported a kind of novel precursors containing Si-N=C=N units as the main chains.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Agents and Synthesis

Silver cyanamide (Ag_2NCN) was synthesized according to literature [9]. Dichlorosilanes and toluene were fresh distilled and all manipulations were conducted in an inert atmosphere.

In a 500ml three neck round bottom flask equipped with a stirrer, a condenser, and a dropping funnel, 12.8g silver cyanamide and 300ml toluene were added. The temperature of the oil bath was raised to reflux toluene for 30 minutes, then dichlorosilanes (typically 7.0ml dichlorodimethylsilane mixed with 50ml toluene) were added dropwise into the flask in 30 minutes. The reaction was sustained for another 2 hours to assure the completion of the reaction, then gravity filtration was applied to remove the precipitate (AgCl) and reduced-pressure distillation (353K/2mmHg) to remove toluene.

Measurement and Instrumentation

Infrared analysis was conducted by using Hitachi 270-30 infrared spectrophotometer (KBr disc). Number average molecular weights (M_n) of samples were measured with a corona 114 molecular weight apparatus by vapor phase osmometry (VPO) in a toluene solution. The molecular weight distributions were measured using a Waters-244 liquid chromatograph with Ultrastaygel as the gel-permeation chromatograph (GPC) column in toluene solution. ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance ($^1\text{H NMR}$) spectra were obtained on an AC-80 high resolution NMR spectrometer at 80 MHz with deuterated chloroform as a solvent and tetramethylsilane as an external reference. Elemental analysis of carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen were performed on a PE2400 CHN elemental analyzer. Thermogravimetric analysis curves were obtained by a Rigaku TGA thermal analyser in $40\text{cm}^3\text{min}^{-1}$ nitrogen flow up to 1273 K at a heating rate of 10Kmin^{-1} .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Structural Elucidation

The reaction, according to the formula, should follow the process:

Me_2SiCl_2 , Ph_2SiCl_2 , MeViSiCl_2 (Vi: $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}_2$), and MeHSiCl_2 were chosen as dichlorosilanes. The properties of synthetic products were listed in Table 1.

Table 1: The properties of synthetic products

Product	Appearance	M_n	n
$[\text{Me}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$	oil	860	8.8
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$	gum	1780	8.0
$[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$	oil	1440	13.1
$[\text{MeHSiNCN}]$	waxy solid	—	—

$[\text{Me}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$, $[\text{Ph}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$, $[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$ dissolved well in benzene, toluene, and xylene. The average number of units in the chains was approximately 10, indicating the products were oligomers or low molecules. The dispersive indexes were around 1.5, showing no cyclic products present.

But $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ dissolved poorly in aromatic solvents, hinting that crosslinking had occurred and branched structure had formed.

Elemental analysis (Table 2) agreed well with theoretical values in the case of $[\text{Me}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$, $[\text{Ph}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$, and $[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$, indicating the supposed structures were reasonable. But for $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ the hydrogen content deviated lower from that of the theoretical value, indicating the existence of the branched structures at the site of the Si atoms due to the loss of hydrogen, which was in accordance with the poor dissolution in aromatic solvents.

Table 2: Elemental analysis results (%wt)

Product	C		H		N		Si	
	exp.	theo.	exp.	theo.	exp.	theo.	exp.	theo.
[Me ₂ SiNCN] _n	37.1	36.7	6.2	6.1	27.9	28.6	28.8	28.6
[Ph ₂ SiNCN] _n	68.4	70.3	4.6	4.5	11.2	12.6	15.8	12.6
[MeViSiNCN] _n	44.7	43.6	5.9	5.4	25.1	25.4	24.3	25.4
[MeHSiNCN] _n	29.0	28.6	2.6	4.8	32.4	33.3	36.0	33.3

The assumed structures were again confirmed by IR patterns (Table 3) and ¹HNMR spectra. For [Me₂SiNCN]_n, characteristic peaks were 2960cm⁻¹(γ_{as}CH₃), 2900cm⁻¹(γ_sCH₃), 2160cm⁻¹(γN=C=N), 1410cm⁻¹(single δ_{as}CH₃), 1260cm⁻¹(δ_sSi-CH₃), and 950cm⁻¹(γSi-N). For [Ph₂SiNCN]_n, peaks at 1630cm⁻¹ and around 1800cm⁻¹ were ascribed to the stretching vibrations of the rings. For [MeViSiNCN]_n vibrations of unsaturated groups were 1600cm⁻¹(γ_sC=C) and 3100cm⁻¹(γ_{as}=CH). For [MeHSiNCN]_n peaks at 2160cm⁻¹ ascribed to Si-H vibration couldn't be distinguished from N=C=N stretching vibration.

For cyanamide, there usually existed two isomers: N=C=N ↔ N-C≡N, which was characterized by double peaks at 2160cm⁻¹. In our experiment, there was only one single peak at 2160cm⁻¹, indicating there was no end groups of N=C=N in the main chains (actually dichlorosilanes were a little excess).

Table 3: The ascription of vibrations in IR patterns

Wave Number(cm ⁻¹)	Ascription
3100m	γ _{as} =CH
2960m	γ _{as} CH ₃
2900m	γ _s CH ₃
2160s	γ _{as} N=C=N and γ _{as} Si-H
1800w	aromatic rings(C-H)
1630w	aromatic rings(C=C)
1610w	γ _{as} C=C
1410s	δ _{as} CH ₃
1260s	δ _s Si-CH ₃
950m	γSi-N

In ¹HNMR there were only simple peaks for [Me₂SiNCN]_n at 0.3ppm(single, broad, strong), for [Ph₂SiNCN]_n at 7.2ppm(single, mediocre strong), for [MeViSiNCN]_n at 0.8ppm(strong, single), 5.8-6.1ppm(double, mediocre strong), and for [MeHSiNCN]_n at 0.8ppm(single, strong), 4.7ppm(single, broad, mediocre strong).

Ceramic Yields Upon Pyrolysis

Ceramic yield is one of the most important index to evaluate the usefulness of the precursor. Generally high ceramic yield is helpful.

The four synthetic polymers were applied to TG to determine the ceramic yield, and the results were listed in Table 4.

As shown above, ceramic yield in $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ was as high as 56%, while in $[\text{Me}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$ was nearly none. Two reasons might contribute to the rather low yields: the linear structures caused segment-after-segment breakage of the main chains and crosslinking for $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ and $[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$ was not enough. Thus $[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$ was crosslinked in N_2 in the presence of 0.5% wt dicumyl peroxide(DCP), then it changed from oil to waxy solid, followed by pyrolysis to obtain 55%wt ceramic. $[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$ was heattreatment at 453K for 6 hours, then was pyrolyzed to obtain 64% ceramic. In Fig. 1 there showed the TG curves for the treated polymers. Large weight loss occurred during 450-1000K, and the crosslinked polymer were rather stable before 450K. The mechanism involved during the pyrolysis is being under study.

Table 4: Char yields upon pyrolysis

Product	Char Yield (wt%)
$[\text{Me}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$	3.6
$[\text{Ph}_2\text{SiNCN}]_n$	27.8
$[\text{MeViSiNCN}]_n$	41.2
$[\text{MeHSiNCN}]_n$	56.0

Fig. 1: TG curves for samples after treatment(ramping rate 10K /min, N_2)

CONCLUSION

By reacting silver cyanamide and chlorosilanes (dimethyldichlorosilane, methylvinyl-dichlorosilane, diphenyldichlorosilane, methyldichlorosilane) in refluxing toluene, the synthetic products which were characterized by IR, ¹HNMR, GPC, and elemental analysis to bear the linear and light branched structure $-(SiRR'N=C=N)-_n$ were obtained. Upon pyrolysis ceramic yields ranged from nearly zero to 56%(wt). Heat treatment of $[MeHSiNCN]_n$ and crosslinking treatment of $[MeViSiNCN]_n$ gave ceramic yields(upon pyrolysis) of 64% and 55%, respectively.

REFERENCES

1. Yajima,S., "Special Heat-Resisting Materials from Organometallic Polymers", *American Ceramic Society Bulletin*, vol.**62**, No.8, 1983, pp.893-898.
2. Suzuki, M., Maniette, Y., Nakata, Y., and Okatani, T., "Synthesis of Silicon Carbide-Silicon Nitride Composite Ultrafine Particles Using a Carbon Dioxide Laser", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol. **76**, No.5, 1993, pp.1195-200.
3. Nakano, K., Kamiya, A., Nishino, Y., Imura, T., and Tsu-Wei, Chou., " Fabrication and Characterization of Three Dimensional Carbon Fiber Reinforced Silicon Carbide and Silicon Nitride Composites", *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, vol.**78**, No.10, 1995, pp.2811-14.
4. Yajima, S., Hesagawa, Y., Okamura, K., Matsuzawa, T., "Development of High-Tensile-Strength Silicon Carbide Fibre Using an Organosilicon Polymer Precursor", *Nature(London)*, vol.**273**, 1978, pp.525-526.
5. Boury,B., Corriu, R.J.P., Leclercq, D., Mutin, H., Planex, J.P., and Vioux, A., "A Catalytic Preparation of a New Pre-ceramic Polymers: Transformation into SiC." **IN: Inorganic and Organometallic Polymers with Special Properties**, Laine, R.M., Ed., Academic Publishers, Netherlands, pp.255-266.
6. Gary, T.B., Timothy, P., Angelotti, L. F., Grish, C., John, A.M., " Alkyl- and Aryl-silylsesquizes: Effects of the R Group on Polymer Degradation and Ceramic Char Composition", *Journal of Material Science*, vol.22, 1987, pp.2609-2614.
7. Mocaer,D., Pailler, R., Naslain, R. et al., "Si-C-N Ceramics with a High Microstructural Stability Elaboration from the Pyrolysis of New Polycarbosilazane Precursors. Part I. The Organic/Inorganic Transition", *Journal of Material Science*,vol. **28** ,1993, pp.2615-2631.
8. Coloumbier, C., and Cuer, J.P., "Preparation of Polysilazanes for Use in Ceramic Production", Fr.Demande FR2633301, 1989.
9. Parshall, G.W.(Editor-in-Chief), *Inorganic Syntheses*, vol.**15**, pp.165, McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc., London, 1974.